

Influence of Stress on a Specific Function

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Abstract

Stress is a factor that causes many diseases. Our article examines the effects of stress on cognitive function, the factors that cause stress, and their elimination.

Keywords: function, stress, cognitive, health, diabetes, obesity.

From the beginning of the article, let's have an understanding of the cognitive functions. Cognitive functions include perception (reception) of information, processing and analysis of information, remembering and storing them later, exchange of information, development and implementation of an action plan. The causes of cognitive disorders can be many diseases that differ in the mechanisms and conditions and course of the disease.

Causes of cognitive impairment.

Cognitive disorders have a functional and organic nature. Functional disorders in the cognitive field are formed in the absence of direct brain damage. Overwork, stress and constant overstrain, negative emotions - all these can be the cause of functional cognitive disorders. Functional cognitive impairment can develop at any age. Such disorders are not considered dangerous and always disappear or their manifestation is significantly reduced after the cause of the disorders is eliminated. However, in some cases, drug therapy may be required. The most common causes of organic pathologies in the cognitive field are: insufficient blood supply to the brain and age or atrophy of the brain mass. Blood supply to the brain is insufficient due to hypertension, cardiovascular pathology and blood vessels. Therefore, it is very important to diagnose these diseases in time and treat them correctly.

Stress and health, the cognitive system are interconnected.

Stress and health.

Glucocorticoids, including cortisol, are important for regulating the immune system and reducing inflammation. While these injuries are valuable in stressful or threatening situations where the immune system can be activated, chronic stress can cause a disruption in communication between the immune system and the HPA axis.

This disrupted communication is associated with the future development of many physical and mental health conditions, including chronic fatigue, metabolic diseases (eg, diabetes, obesity), depression, and immune dysfunction.

Stress can also make it easier to feel pain, bloating or discomfort in the bowels. This can affect how quickly food moves through the body, which can lead to diarrhea or constipation. In addition, stress can cause muscle spasms in the intestines, which can be painful.

Stress can affect digestion and how the intestines absorb nutrients. Gas production associated with nutrient absorption may increase.

The gut has a tough barrier to protect the body from (most) food-borne bacteria. Stress weakens the gut barrier and allows gut bacteria to enter the body. Although most of these bacteria are easily taken care of by the immune system and do not make us sick, the ever-increasing need for an inflammatory response can lead to chronic mild symptoms.

Stress especially affects people with chronic bowel conditions, such as inflammatory bowel disease or irritable bowel syndrome. This may be due to sensitivity of the gut nerves, changes in gut microbiota, changes in how fast food moves through the gut, and/or changes in gut immune responses. At the same time, stress can be beneficial at the same time. Stress can serve an important purpose and even help you survive. For our ancestors, stress was a useful survival motivator that allowed them to avoid real physical threats. That's because it tricks your body into thinking it's in danger and triggers the "fight or flight" survival mode.

Symptoms of stress can affect your body, your thoughts and feelings, and your behavior. Knowing the common signs of stress can help you manage them. Uncontrolled stress can lead to many health problems, including high blood pressure, heart disease, stroke, obesity, and diabetes.

Symptoms of stress can affect your health, even if you don't know it. You may blame the illness for those nagging headaches, sleep problems, malaise, or lack of focus at work. But stress can really be the cause.

Act to manage stress

If you have stress symptoms, taking steps to manage your stress can have many health benefits. Check out many possible stress management tips. For example:

Get regular physical activity on most days of the week.

Practice relaxation techniques. Try deep breathing, meditation, yoga, tai chi or massage. Keep a sense of humor.

Spend time with family and friends.

Set aside time for hobbies. Read a book, listen to music or go for a walk. Schedule time for your passions. Write in a journal. Get enough sleep. Eat a healthy, balanced diet.

Stay away from tobacco and alcohol use, and use of illegal substances.

Aim to find active ways to manage your stress. Idle ways to manage stress that don't get you moving may seem relaxing. But they may make your stress go up over time. Examples are watching television, going on the internet or playing video games. Act to manage stress If you have stress symptoms,

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